

Electronic Structure and Spectra of Indolizine and its Aza Derivatives

ABDUL HAKIM KHAN, SHYAMAL BARAN DATTA, ARCHANA DASGUPTA, APURBA K. PAL and NANDA K. DASGUPTA*

Chemistry Department, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

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Indolizine and its aza derivatives have been studied theoretically using the method of Pariser, Parr and Pople modified by Dewar and Harget. The ground state properties such as bond length, charge density, reactivity and pi-dipole moment and other properties such as ionization potential, electron affinity, half-wave reduction potential and $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra have been predicted and correlated with the experimental results where available.

Indolizine like cyclazines is interesting molecule for theoretical study. It is the prototype of 5/6 ring systems having one bridge-head nitrogen atom and a ten-pi-electron aromatic structure.

Although simple calculations on indolizine and its aza derivative have been presented earlier using HMO-LCAO procedure to determine atom charges and

bond order¹, frontier electron densities², ionization potential³, atom localization energies⁴ and spectral transitions⁵. Gilasso *et al.*⁶ studied indolizine and azaindolines using SCF MO method with CI to predict the π -electronic spectral transitions and correlate them with experimental results. Study of indolizine and its mono-aza and some di-aza derivatives (1-7) using different set of parameters has been reported in this paper. Bond length, charge density, $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectral transitions, ionization potential, electron affinity, half-wave reduction potential of the molecules have been reported. Attempts have been made to correlate them with experimental results where available and also compare them with other works.

Method and parameter : The method has been described

elsewhere⁷. The procedure is the self-consistent field approach due to Pariser and Parr⁸ and Pople⁹ modified by Dewar and Hargett¹⁰ within the zero-differential overlap approximation and using semi-empirical evaluation of integrals. The resonance integral (β_{ij}), the bond length (r_{ij}) and the two-centre two-electron repulsion integrals (γ_{ij}) for bonded atoms were adjusted at each iteration according to the relation,

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PARAMETERS

Bond	K	a/A	b/A	Atom	I_i eV	χ_{ii} eV	Z_{eff}
C-C	6.927	1.512	0.174	C	11.16	11.134	3.18
C-N	6.961	1.448	0.178	N	14.12	12.341	3.55

TABLE 2— $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ SPECTRAL TRANSITIONS, ΔE (eV) AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH (f) OF INDOLIZINE SYSTEM

Molecule	Experimental transitions		Theoretical transitions							
	ΔE	f	Present work S.C.F. method		Present work C.I. method		Other work		Other work	
			ΔE	f	ΔE	f	ΔE	f	ΔE	f
								Ref. 6		Ref. 23
Indolizine	3.58 ^a									
	3.7 ^b	0.039	3.63	0.27	3.72	0.16	3.56	0.092	3.84	0.098
	4.21 ^a									
	4.3 ^b	0.049	4.43	0.32	4.32	0.21	4.3	0.043	4.57	0.095
	5.22 ^a									
	5.4 ^b	0.70	5.35	0.31	5.36	0.82	5.85	1.095	5.94	1.11
1-Aza-	Ref. 22									
indolizine	4.01		3.63	0.27	3.72	0.16	3.91	0.096		
	4.43		4.43	0.32	4.32	0.21	4.42	0.001		
	5.42		5.36				5.94	1.116		
2-Aza-	3.60		3.51	0.34	3.58	0.17	3.45	0.131		
indolizine	4.53		4.27	0.26	4.30	0.29	4.43	0.136		
	5.69		5.58	0.33	5.71	0.34	5.98	0.386		
7-Aza-	Ref. 22									
indolizine	3.66		3.50	0.32	3.69	0.23	3.74	0.09		
	4.38		4.33	0.33	4.22	0.15	4.38	0.09		
	5.52		5.58	0.24	5.54	0.82	5.82	0.60		
1,6-Diaza-	Ref. 23									
indolizine	4.01		3.65	0.20	3.62	0.13	3.90	0.12		
	4.59		4.63	0.21	4.39	0.25	4.41	0.03		
	5.51		5.33	0.30	5.35	0.79	6.09	1.09		
1,7-Diaza-	4.13		3.40	0.28	3.93	0.25	4.07	0.84		
indolizine	4.36		4.02	0.30	4.34	0.13	4.50	0.03		
	5.87		5.84	0.24	5.44	0.80	5.88	1.00		
1,8-Diaza-	3.72		3.55	0.14	3.34	0.18	3.79	0.103		
indolizine	4.47		4.38	0.22	4.34	0.07	4.35	0.026		
	5.45		5.57	0.22	5.33	0.88	5.89	0.80		

^aRef. 22. ^bRef. 6(b).

$$r_{ij} (\text{\AA}) = a - bp_{ij} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\gamma_{ij} = -k_{ij} S_{ij}^{AB} \quad (2)$$

where, p_{ij} is the π -bond order, S_{ij} the overlap integral between $2p_{\pi}$ Slater-type orbitals at centres i and j for nuclei type A and B. The values of parameters a , b and k are given in Table 1. For non-bonded atoms γ_{ij} is set equal to zero. The two-centre two-electron repulsion integrals, γ_{ij} were evaluated from Ohno's formula¹¹. One-centre two-electron integrals (γ_{ij}) were calculated using the relation¹²,

$$\gamma_{ij} = I_i - A_i \quad (3)$$

where, I and A represent the valence state ionization potential and electron affinity of the atoms concerned respectively and the values are taken from the works of Hinze and Jaffe¹³. The values of γ_{ij} and I_i are also included in Table 1. For non-bonded centres γ_{ij} were not varied but were kept at the values calculated from the initial geometry of the molecules assumed to be planar with bond lengths equal to 1.40 Å and bond angles 120° for benzene ring.

Results and Discussion

$\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra, ionisation potential, electron affinity and π -dipole moment : $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra have been studied for these molecules using both SCF and configuration interaction, CI methods. In the CI method, instead of using Ohno's formula for evaluation of two-centre two-electron repulsion integrals the formula of Mataga and Nishimoto¹⁴ was used. Because in the context of configuration interaction, the use of the formula of Mataga and Nishimoto for γ_{ij} is more effective in predicting the $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra for a large number of compounds^{15,16}. The values of K for C-C used in the CI procedure was changed from 6.927 to 9.1846 eV (Ref. 16), and for C-N it is 6.9612 eV, the same as used in the SCF procedure. With this modification, we

utilised the SCF procedure to generate the initial vectors, β -integrals and γ -integrals to be used in the CI procedure where all the configurations arising from one-electron excitations involving orbitals obtained in a prior self-consistent field calculation. The calculated $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectral transitions for these molecules are presented in Table 2 along with the oscillator strength (f), which was obtained from the relation¹⁷,

$$f = 1.085 \times 10^{-5} \bar{\nu} \mu^2 \quad (4)$$

where, $\bar{\nu}$ is the transition energy (cm^{-1}) and μ the dipole length for the corresponding transition (Å). The experimental values are also presented in Table 2. It is clear that the agreement between the experimental transitions and theoretical $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra is good and our works are better than those of others. Especially, transitions predicted by CI method is in very good agreement with the experimental ones.

According to Koopmans' theorem¹⁸, the ionisation potential (IP) can be approximated by the highest occupied orbital energy (e_i). But the predicted value of IP is 1 or 2 eV higher than the experimental value. In case of electron affinity (EA), it can also be approximated by the lowest unoccupied orbital energy (e_j). Here too the predicted value of EA differs from the experimental value of EA by 1 or 2 eV. Hence, a correction term is to be added in both the cases of IP and EA in order to obtain their correct values. The following relations between ionisation potential and highest occupied orbital energy and electron affinity and lowest unoccupied orbital energy are in common use in the literature,

$$\text{IP} = -(e_i + C) \quad (5)$$

and

$$\text{EA} = -(e_j + D) \quad (6)$$

TABLE 3—HEAT OF ATOMISATION (ΔH_a), π -BOND ENERGY ($E_{\pi b}$), RESONANCE ENERGY (RE), IONISATION POTENTIAL (IP), ELECTRON AFFINITY (EA), HALF-WAVE REDUCTION POTENTIAL ($E_{1/2}$) AND π -DIPOLE MOMENT (μ)

Molecule	ΔH_a eV	$E_{\pi b}$ eV	RE eV	RE/bond eV	IP eV	EA eV	$E_{1/2}$ V	μ D
1	76.902	10.602	0.304	0.0304	7.82	0.007	3.42	0.44, 1.80 ^a
2	71.645	10.804	0.344	0.0344	8.32	0.57	2.86	2.45
3	71.619	10.776	0.318	0.0318	7.78	-0.02	3.45	1.41
4	71.619	10.773	0.352	0.0352	8.16	0.50	2.93	1.72
5	66.410	10.982	0.405	0.0405	8.38	0.60	2.83	2.13
6	66.263	10.889	0.259	0.0259	8.70	1.08	2.35	0.31
7	66.445	11.021	0.451	0.0451	8.25	0.98	2.45	4.41

^aRef. 6(b).

where, C and D are correction terms. Birss and Dasgupta¹⁹ used a value of C to be 1.88 eV and they predicted the ionisation potential of a large number of aromatic hydrocarbons and heterocyclic systems. The value of D is 1.38, being the difference between the lowest unoccupied orbital energy and the electron affinity of naphthalene. The predicted values of IP and EA are presented in Table 3 which also contains the calculated value of $E_{1/2}$, the half-wave reduction potential from the relation proposed by Birss and Dasgupta²⁰,

$$E_{1/2} = -0.833e_j - 3.46 \quad (7)$$

The theoretical π -dipole moment calculated by us is also included in Table 3.

Heat of atomisation, bond energy and stability : 'Dewar' resonance energy (RE) has been calculated from the relation,

$$RE = \Delta H_a - \Delta H'_a \quad (8)$$

where, ΔH_a is the heat of atomisation of the molecule and $\Delta H'_a$ the heat of atomisation of the molecule when π -electrons are localised. In the absence of experimental value of ΔH_a , it can be estimated from the relation,

$$\Delta H_a = E_{\pi b} + E_{\sigma b} + n_{C-H} E_{C-H} \quad (9)$$

where, $E_{\pi b}$, $E_{\sigma b}$ and E_{C-H} are the π -bond energy, σ -bond energy and C-H bond energy respectively, and n_{C-H} is the number of C-H bonds. The value of $\Delta H'_a$ has been evaluated from the relation,

$$\Delta H'_a = n' E_{C-C} + n'' E_{C=C} + n_{C-H} E_{C-H} \quad (10)$$

where, n' , n'' , E_{C-C} and $E_{C=C}$ represent the number of C-C bonds, number of C=C bonds, C-C bond energy and C=C bond energy respectively. The values of n_{C-H} and E_{C-H} are the same as in eqn. (9). The values of E_{C-H} , E_{C-C} and $E_{C=C}$ are taken from Dewar and Harget¹⁰. The values of ΔH_a and $E_{\pi b}$, resonance energy and resonance energy per bond (RE/bond) are included in Table 3.

As resonance energy is not very useful in predicting the stability or aromaticity of any molecule, resonance energy per bond has been used in predicting the stability of indolizene systems. Moreover, any similar aromatic heterocyclic compound should be chosen so that resonance energy per bond of the heteroaromatic compound may be used as the basis of the study of aromaticity of the indolizene systems. The reference molecule here is cycl[3,2,2]azine²⁰ which is aromatic. On the basis of the molecule whose resonance energy per bond is equal to 0.0483 (resonance energy per bond of cycl[3,2,2]azine) or higher than that would

be considered to be aromatic. Indolizine having resonance energy per bond, 0.0304, has RE/bond lower than that of cycl[3,2,2]azine. Hence, molecule (1) is not aromatic. Similarly the molecules 2, 3, 4 and 6 have low resonance energy and RE/bond which are less than that of cycl[3,2,2]azine suggesting that the molecules are not aromatic. The molecules 5 and 7 have sufficiently high resonance energy and RE/bond and the values are comparable to those of cycl[3,2,2]azine. As such they might be aromatic. However, in view of lack of experimental evidence conclusion can not be drawn properly.

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